
236. More on interstellar extinction

IN ESSAY 191 (August 2024) I discussed the substantial progress being made, using Gaia data, in characterising interstellar extinction. But a further development recently reported by Zhang & Green (2025), in the journal *Science*, merits specific mention. Their work brings a further improvement to the description of extinction along many lines-of-sight throughout the Galaxy. But it also provides some rather remarkable conclusions about the underlying physical processes involved.

As the authors state in their introduction, interstellar dust plays a major role in many areas of astronomy. . . *'either as a nuisance, or as an object of study in its own right.* Their work brings a new perspective on the latter.

LET ME FIRST summarise some key points from essay 191 by way of background. Interstellar extinction is important in the determination of stellar parameters (e.g. T_{eff} , $\log g$, and $[M/H]$), through spectral modelling), and in describing the distribution of gas and dust in the solar neighbourhood. Light is absorbed and scattered by any gas and dust between star and observer, and most stellar spectra are affected to a greater or lesser extent. The details and spatial variation of the extinction depend on the properties of dust grains along the line-of-sight, and measurements also convey information about their composition and size distribution.

Interstellar extinction is a rather smooth function of wavelength, albeit with superimposed absorption features due to particular chemical species. These include the ultraviolet (217 nm) bump, diffuse interstellar bands, and other features beyond Gaia's response in the infrared. Extinction in a given direction can be inferred by comparing an observed spectrum with its closest atmosphere model. In the solar neighbourhood, extinction in the V -band averages some $0.7\text{--}1.0 \text{ mag kpc}^{-1}$, but it is much higher in specific regions, notably in the Galactic plane, and especially towards the Galactic centre.

Since blue light is more strongly attenuated than red, extinction also causes objects to appear redder as well as dimmer. This 'reddening' is often simply characterised by an object's *colour excess* in some specified photometric system, e.g. $E_{B-V} = (B - V)_{\text{obs}} - (B - V)_0$.

THE PARAMETER $R \equiv A_V/E(B - V)$ characterises the ratio of total-to-selective extinction. Ranging between 2.2–5.8 for sight lines where ultraviolet extinction has been measured, a mean relation $A_V = 3.1 E(B - V)$ is frequently used (e.g. Cardelli et al., 1989; Fitzpatrick, 1999; Fitzpatrick & Massa, 2007).

There is a huge literature on extinction, and advances have benefitted from ultraviolet and infrared observations. Even so, around the time of the Gaia launch, Lallement et al. (2014) noted that *'3d maps of the Galactic interstellar matter are a potential tool of wide use, but accurate and detailed maps are still lacking'*.

Gaia is changing this. Parallaxes provide the fundamental means of quantifying the dependence of extinction on distance for millions of sight lines in the Galaxy. And crucially, reddening and extinction *for each star* can be determined from Gaia's low-resolution BP/RP (aka XP) spectra, and from its RVS spectra.

EARLY Gaia DR2-based work to characterise extinction only had access to the *integrated* photometry, and most studies also included infrared photometry, e.g. using 2MASS and WISE (Andrae et al., 2018; Leike & Enßlin, 2019; Chen et al., 2019; Lallement et al., 2019; Green et al., 2019; Anders et al., 2019; Sun et al., 2022). Improved maps followed from EDR3 (Anders et al., 2022; Lallement et al., 2022; Vergely et al., 2022).

As I detailed in essay 191, major improvements came with DR3, partly from the improved parallaxes, but also with the availability of the mean BP/RP spectra for 220 million stars (Andrae et al., 2023a; Kordopatis et al., 2023; O'Callaghan et al., 2024). Revisions also used improved reductions of the XP spectra for some 100 million stars (Zhang et al., 2023b; Andrae et al., 2023b; Hattori, 2025; An et al., 2024; Gontcharov et al., 2023).

The XP spectra also allow determination of extinction at their intrinsic spectral resolution, $R \sim 20 - 100$. X. Zhang et al. (2023b) constructed a 'universal extinction' versus wavelength curve, with each wavelength interval modelled separately. The resulting smooth extinction dependence (their Fig. 15) agrees reasonably well with the $A_V = 3.1 E(B - V)$ model of Cardelli et al. (1989).

VARIATIONS OF the total-to-selective extinction, $R(V)$, actually provide valuable information on the dust grain properties. Compared to its average of around 3.1, values up to 6 occur along sight lines passing through dense molecular clouds. This has been attributed to the growth of dust grains through accretion and coagulation (e.g. Vrba & Rydgren, 1984; Fitzpatrick, 1999; Draine, 2003; Köhler et al., 2012; Foster et al., 2013). In low-density regions, more exposed to stellar radiation, values as low as 2 have been attributed to grain destruction through sputtering by impinging atoms or ions, and photolysis by ultraviolet photons (e.g. Draine, 2003).

WITH THESE GOALS, Schlafly et al. (2016) examined $R(V)$ for 37 000 stars using spectroscopy from APOGEE combined with photometry from Pan-STARRS1, 2MASS, and WISE. But significantly increased sample sizes are now becoming available. R. Zhang et al. (2023a) selected 3 million stars from LAMOST, supplemented by Gaia photometry, to investigate the relationship between $R(V)$ and parameters such as gas-to-dust ratio, dust temperature, dust emissivity, column densities, and the ratio of atomic to molecular hydrogen.

Their $R(V)$ distribution is well-described by a Gaussian distribution with a mean of 3.25 and a dispersion of 0.25. Within the Galactic disk, $R(V)$ exhibits a wide range on various scale sizes, from small structures within individual molecular clouds to larger scales spanning kpc.

BASED ONLY ON Gaia data, X. Zhang & Green (2025) used the low-resolution BP/RP spectra to measure extinctions, and $R(V)$, for 130 million stars. Rich spatial structure is seen on many length scales (see figure). In the Galactic plane ($|z| < 400$ pc), within 2.6 kpc of the Sun (their Fig. 1), they found spatial correlations between $R(V)$ and several large-scale structures, including the Radcliffe Wave (Alves et al., 2020), the ‘Split’ (Lallement et al., 2019), and the Carina–Sagittarius arm.

There is some interesting physics encoded in these diagrams. Rather than increasing continuously with density (as a simple consequence of growing grain size), they found that $R(V)$ is above average in very diffuse regions, but then *decreases* as the dust density *increases*. But in very dense regions, such as the Orion Nebula and dense cores in Taurus, $R(V)$ increases sharply.

Their explanation involves the two dominant mechanisms of dust grain growth in the interstellar medium: *accretion* of elements from the gas phase onto the grain surfaces, and *coagulation* of grains that collide and stick together, the latter occurring preferentially at higher densities. While both processes increase the average grain size, their effects on the grain-size *distribution*, and thus $R(V)$, are very different (Hirashita, 2012).

In a simplified picture, accretion deposits a layer of equal thickness onto each grain, such that the fractional increase in surface area is larger for smaller grains. The increasing contribution of the small grains causes a steepening of the extinction curve, and hence a decreasing $R(V)$. Coagulation, in contrast, transforms pairs of small grains into larger grains, decreasing the relative abundance of small grains. The extinction curve becomes flatter, thus increasing $R(V)$.

Their results, they argue, are consistent with a picture in which accretion is the dominant mechanism of grain growth in the less dense regions of interstellar clouds, leading to the observed decrease in $R(V)$ with increasing dust density. In the densest regions, coagulation takes over, causing $R(V)$ to increase rapidly.

THE WORK has already had some wider consequences. The extinction curves now require additional dependencies than $R(V)$ alone (Green et al., 2024). It offers the prospects of characterising magnetic field dependencies (Hensley, 2025). And it offers insights into the growth of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons as a consequence of gas-phase accretion (X. Zhang et al., 2025).